

Fuzzy Strongly g^* s Closed sets in Fuzzy Topological spaces

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, we have introduced and study the concept of strongly g^* s closed set in Fuzzy topological spaces and discuss some of its properties.

Keywords and Phrases: Fuzzy set, fuzzy topological spaces, fg -closed set, fuzzy strongly g^* -closed set.

1. Introduction

In 1965 Zadeh introduced the concept of fuzzy sets. Subsequently many researcher have been worked in this area and related areas which have applications in different field based on this concept. As generalizations of topological spaces Chang introduced the concept of fuzzy topological spaces in 1968. Veerakumar introduced and studied g^* closed sets in general topology. Recently Parimezhagan and subramaniapillai introduced strongly g^* -closed sets in topological spaces. In this paper, we have introduced and study the concept of strongly g^* s – closed sets in fuzzy topological spaces and obtained the relationship among the various closed sets.

2. Preliminaries

Definition 2.1: [5] A subset of a topological space (X, τ) is called a fuzzy generalized closed set (briefly fg -closed) if $cl(A) \leq U$ whenever $A \leq U$ and U is fuzzy open in X .

Definition 2.2: [9] A subset of a topological space (X, τ) is called a fuzzy generalized semi closed set (briefly fgs -closed) if $scl(A) \leq U$ whenever $A \leq U$ and U is fuzzy open in X .

Definition 2.3: [12] A subset of a topological space (X, τ) is called a fuzzy semi generalized closed set (briefly fs_g -closed) if $cl(A) \leq U$ whenever $A \leq U$ and U is fuzzy semi- open in X .

Definition 2.4: [4] A subset of a topological space (X, τ) is called a fuzzy g^* -closed set (briefly fg^* -closed) if $cl(int(A)) \leq U$ whenever $A \leq U$ and U is fuzzy gopen in X .

Definition 2.5: [1] A subset of a topological space (X, τ) is called a fuzzy wg -closed set (briefly fwg -closed) if $cl(int(A)) \leq U$ whenever $A \leq U$ and U is fuzzy open in X .

Definition 2.6: [8] A subset of a topological space (X, τ) is called a fuzzy strongly g^* -closed set (briefly strongly fg^* -closed) if $cl(A) \leq U$ whenever $A \leq U$ and U is fuzzy gopen in X .

3. Some Properties of Strongly Generalized closed sets with Respect to an Ideal

In this section we introduce the concept of fuzzy strongly g^* s – closed sets and study some of its properties in fuzzy topological spaces.

Definition 3.1: Let (X, τ) be a fuzzy topological spaces. A fuzzy set A of (X, τ) is called fuzzy strongly g^* s – closed set if $int(scl(A)) \leq U$ whenever $A \leq U$ and U is fuzzy gs -open in X

Theorem 3.2: Every fuzzy closed set is fuzzy strongly g^* s – closed set in a fuzzy topological spaces (X, τ)

Proof: Let A be fuzzy closed set in X. Let H be a fgs open in X such that $A \leq H$. Since A is fuzzy closed, $cl(A) = A$. Therefore $cl(A) \leq H$. Now $int(scl(A)) \leq cl(A) \leq H$. Hence A is fuzzy strongly g^* s – closed set in X.

The converse of the above theorem is not true in general as seen from the following example.

Example 3.3: Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$. Fuzzy sets A and B are defined by $A(a) = 0.7, A(b) = 0.3, A(c) = 0.5; B(a) = 0.7, B(b) = 0.3, B(c) = 0.5$. Let $\tau = \{0, A, 1\}$. Then B is a fuzzy strongly g^* s – closed set but it is not a fuzzy closed set in (X, τ)

Theorem 3.4: Union of two fuzzy strongly g^* s closed set is fuzzy strongly g^* s closed.

Proof: Let A and B be two fuzzy strongly g^* s closed sets in X. Let U be a fgs open in X such that $A \cup B \subseteq U$. Then $A \subseteq U$ and $B \subseteq U$. Since A and B are fuzzy strongly g^* s closed set, $int(scl(A)) \subseteq U$ and $int(scl(B)) \subseteq U$. Hence $int(scl(A \cup B)) = int(scl(A) \cup scl(B)) \subseteq U$. Therefore $A \cup B$ is a fuzzy strongly g^* s closed.

Theorem 3.5: Every fuzzy g – closed is fuzzy strongly g^* s closed set in X.

Proof: Let A be fuzzy g -closed set in X. Let H be a fgs open in X such that $A \leq H$. Since A is fuzzy g -closed, $cl(A) \leq H$. Now $int(scl(A)) \leq cl(A) \leq H$. Hence A is fuzzy strongly g^* s – closed set in X.

The converse need not be true, as this may be seen from the following example.

Example 3.6: Let $X = \{a, b\}$. Fuzzy sets A and B are defined by $A(a) = 0.3, A(b) = 0.3; B(a) = 0.5, B(b) = 0.4$. Let $\tau = \{0, B, 1\}$. Then A is a fuzzy strongly g^* s closed set but it is not a fg closed, since $Cl(B) \not\subseteq B$.

Theorem 3.7: Every fuzzy strongly g^* s closed set is fuzzy g s closed sets in X

Proof: Let A be a fuzzy strongly g^* s closed set in X. Let U be open set such that $A \subseteq U$.

Since every open set is g s open and A is fuzzy strongly g^* s closed. We have $int(scl(A)) \subseteq U$.

Therefore A is fgs closed in X.

The converse of the above theorem is not true in general as seen from the following example.

Example 3.8: Let $X = \{a, b\}$. Fuzzy sets A and B are defined by $A(a) = 0.3, A(b) = 0.3; B(a) = 0.5, B(b) = 0.4$. Let $\tau = \{0, B, 1\}$. Then A is a fuzzy strongly g^* s closed set but it is not a fgs closed, since $sCl(B) \not\subseteq B$.

Theorem 3.9: Every fuzzy strongly g^* s closed set is fuzzy sg closed sets in X

Proof: Let A be a fuzzy strongly g^* s closed in X. Let U be semi-open set such that $A \subseteq U$. Since every semi-open set is g s open and A is fuzzy strongly g^* s closed. We have $int(scl(A)) \subseteq U$.

Therefore A is fsg closed in X.

The converse of the above theorem is not true in general as seen from the following example.

Example 3.10: Let $X = \{a, b\}, \tau = \{0, A, B, D, 1\}$ and fuzzy sets A, B, D and H are defined by $A(a) = 0.2, A(b) = 0.4; B(a) = 0.6, B(b) = 0.7; D(a) = 0.4, D(b) = 0.6; H(a) = 0.4, H(b) = 0.5$. Then H is a fuzzy strongly g^* s-closed set but it is not a sg closed, since $Cl(H) \not\subseteq D$ where as $H \leq D$ and D is fg open.

Theorem 3.11: Every fuzzy strongly g^* s closed set is fuzzy wg -closed sets in X

Proof: Let A be a fuzzy strongly g^* s closed in X. Let U be open set in X such that $A \subseteq U$.

Since every open set is g s open and A is fuzzy strongly g^* s closed. We have $int(scl(A)) \subseteq U$.

Therefore A is fwg -closed in X.

The converse of the above theorem is not true in general as seen from the following example.

Example 3.12: Let $X = \{a, b\}, \tau = \{0, A, B, D, 1\}$ and fuzzy sets A, B, D and H are defined by $A(a) = 0.4, A(b) = 0.2; B(a) = 0.7, B(b) = 0.6; D(a) = 0.6, D(b) = 0.4; H(a) = 0.5, H(b) = 0.4$. Then H is a fuzzy strongly g^* s-closed set but it is not a fwg - closed, since $Cl(int(A)) \not\subseteq D$ where as $H \leq D$ and D is f open in X.

Theorem 3.13: Every fuzzy strongly g^* s closed set is fuzzy g^* closed sets in X

Proof: Let A be a fuzzy strongly g^* s closed in X. Let U be g s open set in X such that $A \subseteq U$.

Since U is g s open set and A is fuzzy strongly g^* s closed. We have $int(scl(A)) \subseteq U$. Therefore A is fuzzy g^* closed in X.

Example 3.14: Let $X = \{a, b\}, \tau = \{0, A, B, 1\}$ and fuzzy sets A, B and H are defined by

$A(a) = 0.3$, $A(b) = 0.6$; $B(a) = 0.5$, $B(b) = 0.6$; $H(a) = 0.5$, $H(b) = 0.7$. Then H is a strongly g^* s closed set but it is not fuzzy g^* closed.

Theorem 3.15: If A is a fuzzy strongly g^* s closed set in (X, τ) and $A \leq B \leq \text{sCl}(\text{Int}(A))$, then B is fuzzy strongly g^* s closed in (X, τ) .

Proof: Let A be a fuzzy strongly g^* s closed in X . Let U be fuzzy open set such that $A \subseteq U$. Since every fuzzy open set is g_s open and A is fuzzy strongly g^* s closed. We have $B \subseteq \text{int}(\text{scl}(A)) \subseteq U$. Therefore B is fg^* s closed in X .

Theorem 3.16: A subset A of X is fuzzy strongly g^* s closed set in (X, τ) if and only if $\text{int}(\text{scl}(A)) - A$ contains no nonempty g_s closed sets in X

Proof: Suppose that F is a non-empty g_s -closed subset of $\text{int}(\text{scl}(A)) - A$. Now $F \subseteq \text{scl}(A) - A$. then $F \subseteq \text{int}(\text{scl}(A)) \cap (1 - A)$. Therefore $F \subseteq \text{int}(\text{scl}(A))$ and $F \subseteq 1 - A$. Since F^c is fuzzy g_s -open and A is fuzzy strongly g^* s -closed, $\text{int}(\text{scl}(A) - F^c)$. That is $F \subseteq \text{int}(\text{scl}(A))$. Since F^c is g_s -open set and A is strongly g^* s closed, $\text{int}(\text{scl}(A)) \subseteq F^c$. (i.e) $F \subseteq \text{int}(\text{scl}(A)) \cap \text{int}(\text{scl}(A))^c$. Hence $F \subseteq \text{int}(\text{scl}(A)) \cap \text{int}(\text{scl}(A))^c = \emptyset$. Thus $\text{int}(\text{scl}(A)) - A$ contains no non empty g_s -closed set.

Conversely, Assume that $\text{int}(\text{scl}(A)) - A$ contains no non empty g_s -closed set. Let $A \subseteq U$, U is g_s -open. Suppose that $\text{int}(\text{scl}(A))$ is not contained in U . then $\text{int}(\text{scl}(A)) \cap U^c$ is a non-empty g_s -closed set and contained in $\text{int}(\text{scl}(A)) - A$. Which is contradiction. Therefore $\text{int}(\text{scl}(A)) \subseteq U$ and hence A is fuzzy strongly g^* s-closed set.

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